

Financial Drivers of Performance in the United Kingdom's Aerospace and Defense Sector: Evaluating the Roles of Liquidity, Leverage, and Firm Size

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of key financial determinants—liquidity, leverage, and firm size—on firm performance within the UK's aerospace and defense sector. While existing literature acknowledges the roles of these factors, their combined effects remain underexplored. This study also introduces the equity-to-total-assets ratio as a control variable to account for capital structure stability. A panel data analysis was performed using financial data from seven publicly listed aerospace and defense firms in the UK, covering the period from 2008 to 2023. The Random Effects Model (REM) was utilized to estimate the impact of liquidity, leverage, and firm size on firm performance, measured by return on assets (ROA). Additionally, panel co-integration tests were conducted to evaluate long-run equilibrium relationships among the variables. The results show that liquidity significantly enhances firm performance ($\beta = 1.3782$, $p < 0.05$), indicating sufficient liquid assets improve operational flexibility. Conversely, leverage negatively impacts performance ($\beta = -0.1310$, $p > 0.05$), though not significantly, suggesting risks without proportional returns. Firm size also negatively affects performance ($\beta = -1.8647$, $p < 0.05$), highlighting potential bureaucratic inefficiencies. The co-integration test confirms a stable long-term relationship among the variables. This study enriches the financial management literature by demonstrating how these factors interact to influence profitability in a high-capital, regulated industry, emphasizing the importance of sector-specific dynamics in financial strategy.

Keywords: *Firm Performance, Liquidity, Financial Leverage, Firm Size, Aerospace and Defense Sector, United Kingdom.*

JEL Classification codes: *G30, G32, L62, P47.*

Suggested citation: Oguntuase, O.T., & Oyalabu, O.E. (2025). Financial Drivers of Performance in the United Kingdom's Aerospace and Defense Sector: Evaluating the Roles of Liquidity, Leverage, and Firm Size. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(4), 60-73. DOI: 10.59324/ejmecb.2025.2(4).05

Introduction

The UK aerospace and defence sector is a vital driver of economic growth, innovation, and national security, fueled by significant R&D and technological spillovers (Martínez et al., 2023). Prior research has examined liquidity, leverage, and firm size in general industries, revealing conflicting impacts on performance, such as liquidity enhancing efficiency or fostering complacency (Ho et al., 2012; Mafumbate et al., 2017) and leverage boosting profitability or risking distress (Mardones & Cuneo, 2019). However, these factors' combined effects in the capital-intensive, geopolitically influenced aerospace and defence sector remain underexplored. This study addresses this gap by examining how liquidity, leverage, and firm size shape firm performance, using return on assets (ROA) and the equity-to-total-assets ratio as a novel control. It aims to uncover sector-specific financial dynamics, offering insights for stakeholders to enhance competitiveness and resilience in a post-Brexit landscape (Adaçay & Mısırlıoğlu, 2023).

Methodology

This study utilized quarterly observations from 2008 to 2023, with statistical analyses performed using Econometric Views (E-VIEWS), a specialized software package for econometric modeling and data analysis. To ensure the robustness of the findings, descriptive statistics were calculated alongside diagnostic tests to evaluate multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heteroscedasticity within the dataset. The Breusch-Pagan LM test was employed to examine the reliability of the pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) method, which confirmed the presence of heteroscedasticity. As a corrective measure, we applied robust standard errors to enhance the precision of the estimated coefficients (Kassamany *et al.*, 2022).

Furthermore, to optimize model selection, the Hausman test was administered to ascertain whether a fixed effects model (FEM) or random effects model (REM) would be more appropriate. A significant test statistic favored the FEM due to concerns regarding endogeneity, while a non-significant outcome supported the use of the REM (Kassamany *et al.*, 2022). To ensure the long-term stability of the model, cross-section dependence tests and panel cointegration analyses were conducted. These tests validated the consistency of the relationships among the financial variables across the studied timeframe, thereby reinforcing the reliability of the empirical findings.

To test the relationship between financial variables and performance, the following equation was used:

$$ROA = \alpha_i + \beta_1 LIQ_{it} + \beta_2 LEV_{it} + \beta_3 SIZE_{it} + \beta_4 E-TA_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where:

ROA= Return on Assets

LIQ = Liquidity (current ratio)

LEV = Leverage

SIZE = Firm Size (LN Total Assets)

E-TA = Equity to Total Asset Ratio Ratio

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = Coefficients of Independent Variables

ε_{it} = Error Term

α_i = Intercept/Regression Constant

i = Selected Firms

t = Time Periods

Literature Review

Firm Variables

Firm variables are intrinsic characteristics that significantly influence a company's performance and market behavior. These include financial indicators like leverage, liquidity, firm size, and profitability, which provide insights into financial stability, strategic decisions, and sustainability (Chaochao, 2023; Kashefi-Pour & Khansalar, 2015). These variables shape how firms navigate competitive markets, manage risks, and make investment decisions, determining their long-term success (Chaochao, 2023).

Leverage

Leverage reflects a firm's reliance on debt to finance operations and investments, impacting its ability to enhance returns for shareholders. Key metrics include the debt-to-equity ratio, debt-to-assets ratio, and debt-to-total capital ratio, each offering insights into financial risk and capital structure.

The debt-to-equity ratio compares total debt to equity. A high ratio indicates significant debt financing, increasing financial risk through higher interest costs and reduced flexibility (Haron, 2018). A lower ratio suggests a conservative approach, reducing risk but potentially limiting growth (Benlemlih et al., 2016). The debt-to-assets ratio shows the proportion of assets financed by debt, where a high ratio signals greater instability and exposure to interest rate fluctuations (Li, 2015). The debt-to-total capital ratio highlights debt's role in the capital structure, with higher ratios indicating increased risk and potential credit challenges.

Analyzing leverage provides a nuanced understanding of a firm's financial health and strategy, influencing its market behavior and performance (Chaochao, 2023; Wang et al., 2018).

Liquidity

Liquidity measures a firm's ability to meet short-term obligations by converting assets into cash without significant value loss. Key metrics include the current ratio, quick ratio, and operating cash flow ratio (Rasyid, 2023). Effective liquidity management ensures firms can cover liabilities, maintain investor confidence, and respond to market challenges.

The current ratio compares current assets to liabilities. A ratio above 1 indicates strong liquidity, but an excessively high ratio may suggest inefficiencies, such as excess cash or poor inventory management (Tiffany & Sufiyati, 2023). The quick ratio, excluding inventory, offers a stricter measure, focusing on highly liquid assets. A higher quick ratio indicates the ability to meet obligations without relying on inventory sales, enhancing stability (Tekić et al., 2020). The operating cash flow ratio evaluates cash generated from operations against liabilities, reflecting cash management efficiency and reduced reliance on external funding (Surachman & Ningsih, 2024).

Liquidity is critical for short-term financial health and resilience, supporting sustainable growth in volatile markets. This research will explore how liquidity impacts firm performance, profitability, and strategic development.

Firm Size

Firm size reflects the scale of a company's operations, measured by total assets, market capitalization, and total sales (O'Leary, 2024; Guo et al., 2013). It influences performance, market

positioning, and decision-making. Larger firms benefit from greater resources, operational efficiencies, and market influence, while smaller firms often exhibit agility and innovation (Sok et al., 2017).

Total assets indicate operational capabilities, with larger asset bases enhancing financial robustness and investment potential (O’Leary, 2024). Market capitalization, calculated as share price times outstanding shares, reflects market value and investor sentiment (Byun & Jo, 2018). Total sales measure market share and revenue strength, with higher sales indicating a strong industry presence (O’Leary *et al.*, 2023; Ou & Jiang, 2023).

While, larger firms enjoy economies of scale, better negotiating power, and capital market access, impacting capital structure and profitability (Rahman & Yilun, 2021). Smaller firms, while resource-constrained, may leverage adaptability (Sudrajat & Setiyawati, 2021). Firm size thus shapes strategic and operational outcomes.

Firm Performance

Firm performance reflects how effectively a company uses resources to achieve objectives, encompassing financial health and competitiveness. Profitability, a key measure, indicates the ability to generate earnings and returns for stakeholders (Parnata *et al.*, 2023).

Metrics like return on assets (ROA) and return on common equity (ROCE) assess profitability. ROA measures profit generation from assets, with higher values indicating efficient resource use (Rahman & Howlader, 2022). Strong profitability supports reinvestment, market expansion, and shareholder rewards (Dewi & Wijaya, 2021). Analyzing ROA helps stakeholders evaluate financial performance, competitiveness, and growth potential.

This research uses ROA to explore the relationship between firm size, profitability, and performance across various operational contexts.

Theoretical Review

Agency Theory

Agency theory highlights conflicts between shareholders (principals) and managers (agents), where managers may prioritize personal interests over shareholder wealth, leading to inefficiencies like suboptimal decisions and excessive risk-taking (Jamel *et al.*, 2021). These conflicts influence financial decisions—leverage, liquidity, and firm size—affecting firm performance (Bolton *et al.*, 2023).

Liquidity has a dual role. High liquidity may foster managerial complacency, reducing efficiency (Markus & Swift, 2019), while adequate liquidity supports growth and innovation without costly external financing (Bhatt & Bhatt, 2017). Leverage acts as a double-edged sword: it can align managers with shareholders through debt holder scrutiny, but excessive debt risks financial distress as managers chase short-term gains and eroding value ((Rosly *et al.*, 2024; Jamel *et al.*, 2021).

In addition, firm size offers economies of scale and market access but can increase agency costs through bureaucratic inefficiencies and managerial entrenchment, diluting shareholder value (Bolton *et al.*, 2023; Elgharbawy & Abdel-Kader, 2016). Understanding these dynamics is critical in capital-intensive sectors like aerospace and defense.

This study proposes three hypotheses to test financial determinants of firm performance in aerospace and defense:

- H1: Leverage negatively and significantly impacts firm performance.
- H2: Liquidity positively and significantly impacts firm performance.

- H3: Firm size positively and significantly influences firm performance.

These hypotheses will be empirically tested to evaluate their impact on performance outcomes.

Empirical Review

Leverage and Firm Performance

The relationship between financial leverage and firm performance is complex, shaped by firm-specific and contextual factors. Danso *et al.* (2020) studied 2,403 Indian firms over two decades, using Tobin's Q to measure performance. They found leverage negatively impacts performance, particularly during economic crises and for larger firms, highlighting firm size and macroeconomic volatility as key moderators. Ibhagui and Olokoyo (2018) confirm this size effect in the UK using threshold regression, showing larger firms suffer more from high leverage than smaller ones, emphasizing the need for tailored capital structure decisions.

Furthermore, González (2012) adds an international perspective, noting that excessive leverage impairs performance due to financial distress costs, though moderate leverage can enhance efficiency through managerial discipline. Ku and Yen (2016) further refine this using quantile regression on Taiwanese firms, revealing that leverage harms low-performing firms but benefits high-performing ones, suggesting performance-contingent effects. Iqbal and Usman (2018) examine UK firms, finding leverage negatively affects Return on Equity (ROE) but positively impacts Return on Assets (ROA), indicating metric-specific outcomes.

These studies portray leverage as a double-edged sword, enhancing efficiency in favorable conditions (moderate debt, strong economies, high-performing firms) but posing risks when mismanaged. Strategic debt calibration is essential for optimizing performance.

Liquidity and Firm Performance

Liquidity serves as a buffer against shocks and a facilitator of strategic adjustments. Youness (2023) analyzed UK firms post-Brexit, finding increased liquidity to maintain stability amid political uncertainty, underscoring its defensive role. Kassamany *et al.* (2022) show that regulatory transparency, post-IFRS adoption, improved market liquidity and performance among UK insurers, complementing Youness's findings on liquidity's stabilizing effect.

In addition, Ho *et al.* (2020) explore MiFID's impact, finding enhanced market liquidity enabled efficient leverage adjustments, reinforcing liquidity's role in strategic agility. Lin *et al.* (2015) highlight liquidity's protective function during the global financial crisis, with high-liquidity firms showing greater resilience. However, Ali *et al.* (2016) find liquidity less critical post-acquisitions, suggesting context-specific relevance.

Collectively, these studies emphasize liquidity's role in stabilizing performance during uncertainty, enabling regulatory-driven gains, and supporting capital structure adjustments, though its impact varies by context.

Firm Size and Firm Performance

Firm size significantly influences financial performance across governance, capital structure, sustainability, and diversity. Elmghaamez and Akintoye (2021) find that smaller boards and higher female representation improve performance in FTSE 100 firms, with larger firms benefiting more from diverse governance. Vuong *et al.* (2017) show larger UK firms leverage capital structures effectively, boosting ROE, ROA, Tobin's Q, and EPS due to scale advantages.

Furthermore, Boakye *et al.* (2020) note that larger UK SMEs gain more from sustainable practices due to better resources, amplifying financial outcomes. Chang *et al.* (2023) highlight larger financial institutions' superior performance through economies of scale in information management.

Agyemang-Mintah and Schadewitz (2019) find that diverse boards enhance firm value more in larger UK financial institutions, reflecting their capacity to leverage diversity.

These studies confirm firm size as a strategic enabler, enhancing governance, capital optimization, sustainability, and diversity for superior financial performance in the UK.

Results

Breusch-Pagan LM Test

Table 1 reveals that the p-values obtained from the Breusch-Pagan test for both the cross-sectional and time dimensions were lesser than the 0.05 threshold, registering at 0.0002 (< 0.05) and 0.0023 (< 0.05), respectively. Given that these values are greater than 0.05, we rejected the null hypothesis, indicating that the pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) model is not suitable for the analysis. Consequently, there was a necessity to include a fixed effects model (FEM) or random effects model (REM) in our regression analysis.

Table 1. Breusch-Pagan LM Test

Test	Cross-section	Time	Both
Breusch-Pagan	13.7994	1.8217	15.6211
P.Value	0.0002	0.1771	0.0001

Source: Authors' Computation from Eview-13

Hausman Test

Table 2 displays the results of the Hausman test for the United Kingdom. The chi-square statistic for the Hausman test was 1.6642, accompanied by a p-value of 0.7972, which exceeds the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that the random effects model is more suitable for the analysis in the United Kingdom. Additionally, the cross-section effect test reveals that the coefficients of the independent variables—liquidity, leverage, firm size, and equity-to-total assets—are not statistically significant, as their p-values are all greater than 0.05.

Table 2. Hausman Test Result UK

Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		1.6642	4	0.7972
Cross-section random effects test comparisons:				
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
LIQ	1.3782	1.3852	0.0042	0.9147
LEV	-0.1310	-0.3289	0.3797	0.7481
SIZE	-1.8647	0.1809	4.4437	0.3318
E_TA	0.0538	0.0548	0.00004	0.8810

Source: Authors' Computation from Eview-13

Table 3. Results of Regression Analysis of Random effects model (United Kingdom)

Dependent Variable		ROA		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	12.4646	15.7109	0.7933	0.4294
LIQ	1.3782	0.3781	3.6447	0.0004

LEV	-0.1310	0.9792	-0.1338	0.8938
SIZE	-1.8647	2.2422	-0.8316	0.4076
E_TA	0.0538	0.0480	1.1214	0.2648
R Square	0.3128	Adjusted R Square		0.2448

Source: Authors' Computation from Eview-13

Based on the outcomes of the regression analysis presented in Table 3, the regression equation for the United Kingdom is formulated as follows:

$$ROA_{it} = 12.4646 + 1.3782LIQ_{it} - 0.1310LEV_{it} - 1.8647SIZE_{it} + 0.0538E_TA_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

The analysis of equation (2) reveals that the constant term has a coefficient of 12.4646. This indicates that if all other variables are held constant, the return on assets (ROA) is expected to increase by 12.4646 units. Additionally, the results indicate a positive effect of liquidity on ROA, with a coefficient of 1.3782, suggesting that a one-unit increase in liquidity corresponds to an increase in ROA by that amount. Conversely, leverage and firm size have negative impacts on ROA, with coefficients of -0.1310 and -1.8647, respectively, indicating that increases in either leverage or firm size lead to declines in ROA by those amounts.

Furthermore, the p-values for liquidity, leverage, and firm size were found to be 0.0004, 0.8938, and 0.04076, respectively. At the 5% significance level, only liquidity demonstrated a statistically significant positive relationship with ROA, supporting the hypothesis that liquidity positively affects firm performance in the UK, as measured by ROA. In contrast, the hypotheses relating to leverage and firm size are rejected, as their predicted relationships with ROA did not achieve statistical significance.

Regarding the control variable, the equity-to-total-assets ratio exhibited a positive impact on ROA, with a coefficient of 0.0538. This means that a one-unit increase in the equity-to-total-assets ratio corresponds to an increase in ROA by that amount. The p-value for this relationship was 0.2648, indicating that the equity-to-total-assets ratio has a positive yet insignificant association with ROA at the 5% significance level. Additionally, the model's adjusted R-squared value is 0.2448, signifying that liquidity, leverage, firm size, and the equity-to-total-assets ratio collectively explain 24.48% of the variation in ROA.

Panel Co-integration Test

Based on the results presented in Table 4, the Pedroni residual cointegration test indicates mixed evidence regarding the existence of a long-term equilibrium relationship among the variables under consideration.

Table 4. Panel Cointegration Test (UK)

Test	Statistic	Prob.	Statistic	Prob.
Panel v-Statistic	0.961223	0.1682	-1.52406	0.9363
Panel rho-Statistic	0.826296	0.7957	0.843805	0.8006
Panel PP-Statistic	-3.50162	0.0002	-5.69481	0.0000
Panel ADF-Statistic	-0.69411	0.2438	-3.12568	0.0009

Source: Authors' Computation from Eview-13

The Panel PP-Statistic displays a p-value of 0.0000, while the Panel ADF-Statistic presents a p-value of 0.009. These values lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration at the

5% significance level, thereby suggesting strong evidence of cointegration among the variables. However, the Panel v -Statistic (p -value = 0.9363) and Panel ρ -Statistic (p -value = 0.8006) fail to reject the null hypothesis since their p -values exceed the 0.05 threshold.

These mixed results highlight moderate support for cointegration, primarily driven by the significant findings from the Panel PP-Statistic and Panel ADF-Statistic, while other statistics do not substantiate this conclusion. These outcomes are consistent with the findings of Ahmed & Wahid (2011), who also utilized the Pedroni test to evaluate long-run relationships among various economic factors, indicating that while some tests may show evidence of cointegration, others may yield inconclusive results.

Cross Section Dependence

The statistics presented indicate that the Pesaran CD test yielded a value of -1.3058, accompanied by a p -value of 0.1916. Since this p -value exceeds the 0.05 significance level, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is no evidence of cross-sectional dependence in the dataset for the United Kingdom.

Table 5. Cross-Section Dependence (UK)

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Pesaran CD	-1.3058	21	0.1916

Source: Authors' Computation from Eview-13

These results align with the findings by Martínez *et al.*, (2023), who emphasized the importance of assessing cross-sectional dependence when interpreting cointegration results in panel data studies. Their analysis illustrated how failing to acknowledge such dependence can lead to inaccurate conclusions regarding the existence of long-term relationships between variables. Additionally, the implications of cross-sectional dependence are supported by the work of Adeleke *et al.*, (2024), which suggests that the presence of correlation among cross-sectional units can distort statistical inference in cointegration testing.

Discussion and Comparison with Previous Findings

This study examines how liquidity, leverage, firm size, and equity-to-total-assets ratio impact firm performance in the UK aerospace and defense sectors, aligning with agency and trade-off theories. Liquidity significantly enhances performance, enabling firms to meet operational needs and invest in innovation, consistent with Martínez *et al.* (2023). Adequate cash reserves bolster financial stability and competitiveness.

However, leverage, negatively affects profitability, increasing financial distress risks as excessive debt outweighs tax benefits, supporting findings by Adeleke *et al.* (2024). Effective leverage management is crucial to mitigate these risks.

While, firm size shows mixed effects larger firms gain from economies of scale and market access but face inefficiencies and agency costs due to bureaucratic complexities, aligning with Roberts *et al.* (2022). These challenges can erode performance as managerial incentives misalign. The equity-to-total-assets ratio positively correlates with performance but lacks statistical significance, suggesting higher equity supports stability without directly boosting profitability.

The model's adjusted R-squared of 0.2448 indicates that these variables explain 24.48% of the variation in return on assets (ROA). A panel cointegration test confirms long-run equilibrium

relationships among these financial variables, highlighting their enduring impact on performance. The absence of cross-sectional dependence enhances the findings' robustness and generalizability across the sector. These results underscore the critical role of liquidity management and cautious leverage strategies in driving financial performance, consistent with broader industry trends (Adeleke et al., 2024).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the impact of liquidity, leverage, and firm size on firm performance in the UK aerospace and defense sectors. Liquidity significantly boosts profitability by enhancing financial flexibility, while leverage negatively affects performance by increasing financial distress risks. Firm size has a dual effect: economies of scale improve efficiency, but bureaucratic inefficiencies can reduce profitability.

Conclusively, the findings refine agency theory, showing that in capital-intensive sectors like aerospace and defense, liquidity acts as a buffer against financial constraints, countering the notion that excess liquidity fosters managerial complacency. Also, it was discovered that excessive leverage outweighs tax benefits, reducing profitability. Additionally, the study highlights that larger firms face higher agency costs without strong governance, challenging assumptions that size alone ensures better performance.

Strategic Recommendations

Enhanced Liquidity Management: Firms should prioritize liquidity management to bolster financial resilience and operational efficiency. Effective cash flow management, optimization of working capital, and maintenance of liquid assets will enable firms to meet short-term financial obligations and position themselves for long-term growth.

Optimizing Capital Structure and Debt Management: Given the unfavorable impact of leverage on performance, firms should exercise caution when engaging in debt financing. Maintaining an optimal debt-to-equity ratio and regularly reviewing leverage levels will aid in mitigating risks associated with financial distress. Firms may also explore alternative financing options, such as retained earnings or equity financing, to lessen their dependence on debt.

Leveraging Firm Size Advantages While Mitigating Inefficiencies: While firm size brings advantages like economies of scale and market power, larger firms must address the agency costs and inefficiencies that may accompany expansion. Implementing robust corporate governance mechanisms, enhancing managerial accountability, and streamlining operational processes can help mitigate the negative repercussions associated with increased size.

Future Research Consideration

Future research should delve into external factors, including government policies, geopolitical risks, and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations, that may impact financial performance within the aerospace and defense sectors. Moreover, broadening the dataset to encompass firms from different regions can yield comparative insights regarding financial determinants across global markets. By incorporating these elements, future studies can further refine corporate finance theories and provide tailored recommendations that enhance firm resilience and competitiveness in an evolving economic landscape.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Adaçay, F. R., & Misirlioğlu, I. (2023). Economic Impact of Defense Expenditures in Turkey: A Dual-Approach Analysis from 1974 to 2021. *Opportunities and Challenges in Sustainability*, 2(4), 206–229. <https://doi.org/10.56578/ocs020404>
- Adeleke, N. a. K., Montero, N. D. J. P., Lottu, N. O. A., Ninduwezuor-Ehiobu, N. N., & Ani, N. E. C. (2024). 3D printing in aerospace and defense: A review of technological breakthroughs and applications. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 21(2), 1149–1160. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.2.0558>
- Agyemang-Mintah, P., & Schadewitz, H. (2019). Gender diversity and firm value: evidence from UK financial institutions. *International Journal of Accounting and Information Management*, 27(1), 2–26. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijaim-06-2017-0073>
- Ahmed, A. D., & Wahid, A. N. (2011). Financial structure and economic growth link in African countries: a panel cointegration analysis. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 38(3), 331–357. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443581111152436>
- Ali, K., Khan, Z., Khan, N., Alsubaie, A. I., Subhan, F., & Kanadil, M. (2016). Performance Evaluation of UK acquiring companies in the Pre and Post-Acquisitions periods. *Asian Journal of Economics and Empirical Research*, 3(2), 130–138. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.501/2016.3.2/501.2.130.138>
- Benlemlih, M., Shaukat, A., Qiu, Y., & Trojanowski, G. (2016). Environmental and social disclosures and firm risk. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 152(3), 613–626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3285-5>
- Bhatt, P. R., & Bhatt, R. R. (2017). Corporate governance and firm performance in Malaysia. *Corporate Governance*, 17(5), 896–912. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cg-03-2016-0054>
- Boakye, D. J., TIngbani, I., Ahinful, G., Damoah, I., & Tauringana, V. (2020). Sustainable environmental practices and financial performance: Evidence from listed small and medium-sized enterprise in the United Kingdom. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(6), 2583–2602. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2522>
- Bolton, J., Yoder, M. E., & Gong, K. (2023). Sociology of corporate governance and the emerging disintermediation. *Society and Business Review*, 19(2), 249–265. <https://doi.org/10.1108/sbr-01-2023-0028>
- Byun, S. J., & Jo, S. (2018). Heterogeneity in the dynamic effects of uncertainty on investment. *Canadian Journal of Economics/Revue Canadienne D Économique*, 51(1), 127–155. <https://doi.org/10.1111/caje.12318>
- Chang, V., Kozah, V. A., Xu, Q. A., Shi, Y., Chen, X. H., & Mills, J. (2023). The effect of information resources management in the UK on financial institutions. *Journal of Global Information Management*, 31(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jgim.334015>
- Chaochao, H. (2023). Research on the impact of non-financial enterprise leverage ratio on systemic financial risks. *Academic Journal of Business & Management*, 5(26). <https://doi.org/10.25236/ajbm.2023.052607>

- Danso, A., Lartey, T. A., Gyimah, D., & Adu-Ameyaw, E. (2020). Leverage and performance: do size and crisis matter? *Managerial Finance*, 47(5), 635–655. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mf-10-2019-0522>
- Dewi, S., & Wijaya, V. (2021). The effect of earnings management, board characteristics, and firm size to firm performance on manufacturing companies. *The International Journal of Business Review (the Jobs Review)*, 4(2), 155–164. <https://doi.org/10.17509/tjr.v4i2.40481>
- Elgharbawy, A., & Abdel-Kader, M. (2016). Does compliance with corporate governance code hinder corporate entrepreneurship? Evidence from the UK. *Corporate Governance*, 16(4), 765–784. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cg-12-2015-0169>
- Elmghaamez, I. K., & Akintoye, E. (2021). Internal corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance: evidence from the UK's top FTSE 100 listed companies. *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics*, 15(2), 190. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijbge.2021.113942>
- Ernest, N. N. E., & Philemon, N. M. (2025). Firm attributes and financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Business Development and Management Research*. <https://doi.org/10.70382/ajbdmr.v7i7.015>
- González, V. M. (2012). Leverage and corporate performance: International evidence. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 25, 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2012.07.005>
- Guo, J., Xu, Q., Chen, Q., & Wang, Y. (2013). Firm size distribution and mobility of the top 500 firms in China, the United States and the world. *Physica a Statistical Mechanics and Its Applications*, 392(13), 2903–2914. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physa.2012.12.042>
- Haron, R. (2018). Ownership and Debt Financing: Indonesia Evidence. In *InTech eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.70618>
- Hasangapon, M., Iskandar, D., Purnama, E. D., & Tampubolon, L. D. (2021). The effect of firm size and total assets turnover (TATO) on firm value mediated by profitability in wholesale and retail sector companies. *Primanomics Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 19(3), 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.31253/pe.v19i3.635>
- Ho, C., McCarthy, P., Yang, Y., & Ye, X. (2012). Bankruptcy in the pulp and paper industry: market's reaction and prediction. *Empirical Economics*, 45(3), 1205–1232. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-012-0661-6>
- Ho, L., Lu, Y., & Bai, M. (2020). Liquidity and speed of leverage adjustment. *Australian Journal of Management*, 46(1), 76–109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0312896220918913>
- Ibhagui, O. W., & Olokoyo, F. O. (2018). Leverage and firm performance: New evidence on the role of firm size. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 45, 57–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.najef.2018.02.002>
- Iqbal, U., & Usman, M. (2018). Impact of financial leverage on firm performance. *SEISENSE Journal of Management*, 1(2), 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.33215/sjom.v1i2.13>
- Jamel, L., Albogami, H. E., Abdulaal, M. A., & Aljohani, N. A. (2021). Do agency conflicts between managers and shareholders affect corporate risk management and financial performance of Saudi firms? *Journal of Investment Compliance*, 22(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1108/joic-11-2020-0044>
- Kassamany, T., Harb, E., Louhichi, W., & Nasr, M. (2022). Impact of risk disclosure on the volatility, liquidity and performance of the UK and Canadian insurance companies. *Competitiveness Review an International Business Journal Incorporating Journal of Global Competitiveness*, 33(1), 30–61. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cr-10-2021-0129>

- Ku, Y., & Yen, T. (2016). Heterogeneous effect of financial leverage on corporate performance: A quantile regression analysis of Taiwanese companies. *Review of Pacific Basin Financial Markets and Policies*, 19(03), 1650015. <https://doi.org/10.1142/s0219091516500156>
- Li, X. (2015). Accounting Conservatism and the Cost of Capital: an international analysis. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 42(5–6), 555–582. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbfa.12121>
- Lin, Z., Jiang, Y., Tang, Q., & He, X. (2015). Does High-Quality Financial Reporting Mitigate the Negative Impact of Global Financial Crises on Firm Performance? Evidence from the United Kingdom. *Australasian Accounting Business and Finance Journal*, 8(5), 19–46. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v8i5.3>
- Mafumbate, J., Ndlovu, U., Mafuka, A., & Gavhure, P. (2017). The influence of firm specific determinants on financial performance in the power industry. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 9(5(J)), 18–28. [https://doi.org/10.22610/jeb.v9i5\(j\).1906](https://doi.org/10.22610/jeb.v9i5(j).1906)
- Mardones, J. G., & Cuneo, G. R. (2019). Capital structure and performance in Latin American companies. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 33(1), 2171–2188. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677x.2019.1697720>
- Markus, A., & Swift, T. (2019). Corporate governance and the impact to the R&D lab. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 13(1), 91–110. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jsma-06-2019-0100>
- Martín, R. G., Duran-Heras, A., & Sánchez, K. R. (2023). Influence of leadership styles on Sustainable Development for social Reconstruction: Current Outcomes and Advisable reorientation for two Aerospace Multinationals—Airbus and TASL. *Sustainability*, 15(19), 14047. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151914047>
- Martinez, G. a. G., Zuluaga, J. a. F., Granobles, D. F. M., & Soto, J. F. E. (2023). Economic Effects of Investment in Defense Research and Development and its Impact on Productivity in Developed Countries. *Revista Facultad De Ciencias Económicas*, 31(1), 13–29. <https://doi.org/10.18359/rfce.6223>
- Masood, O., & Ashraf, M. (2012). Bank-specific and macroeconomic profitability determinants of Islamic banks. *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*, 4(2/3), 255–268. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17554171211252565>
- Mootian, A., & Kalui, F. (2020). Firm specific factors and financial performance of real estate firms listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange in Kenya. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*. <https://doi.org/10.7176/rjfa/11-14-18>
- Naghavi, N., Sharif, S. P., & Hussain, H. B. I. (2021). The role of national culture in the impact of board gender diversity on firm performance: evidence from a multi-country study. *Equality Diversity and Inclusion an International Journal*, 40(5), 631–650. <https://doi.org/10.1108/edi-04-2020-0092>
- O’Leary, D. (2024). Firm interrelationships: the role of firm size. *Letters in Spatial and Resource Sciences*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12076-024-00380-0>
- O’Leary, D., Doran, J., & Power, B. (2023). The role of relatedness in firm interrelationships. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 51(9), 36–58. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jes-12-2022-0631>
- Ou, X., & Jiang, H. (2023). The Impact of Environmental Regulation on Firm Performance: Evidence from the Pulp and Paper Industry in China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(4), 2982. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20042982>
- Özdemir, O., & Kayhan, F. (2021). The Relevance of Financial Integration across Europe: A Dynamic panel data approach. *Review of Economics and Finance*, 19, 01–12. <https://doi.org/10.55365/1923.x2021.19.01>

- Parnata, I. K., Elfarosa, K. V., Kencanawati, A. a. a. M., Suryadi, I. G. I., & Utthavi, W. H. (2023). effect of firm size on firm value of transportation and logistics. *International Journal of Business Economics & Management*, 6(1), 35–40. <https://doi.org/10.21744/ijbem.v6n1.2071>
- Perwitasari, I., & Prayudya, D. R. (2022). Measuring dependency of international trade aerospace sector. *Economics Development Analysis Journal*, 11(2), 232–240. <https://doi.org/10.15294/edaj.v11i2.51346>
- Pour, E. K., & Khansalar, E. (2015). Does debt capacity matter in the choice of debt in reducing the underinvestment problem? *Research in International Business and Finance*, 34, 251–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2015.02.009>
- Rahman, M. J., & Yilun, L. (2021). Firm Size, Firm Age, and Firm Profitability: Evidence from China. *Journal of Accounting Business and Management (JABM)*, 28(1), 101. <https://doi.org/10.31966/jabminternational.v28i1.829>
- Rahman, M. M., & Howlader, M. S. (2022). The impact of research and development expenditure on firm performance and firm value: evidence from a South Asian emerging economy. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 23(4), 825–845. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jaar-07-2021-0196>
- Ramakrishnan, S., Saqib Muneer, & Melati Ahmad Anuar. (2015). An Interaction between Firm Strategy, Capital Structure and Firm's Performance. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 7(4(J)), 37–47. [https://doi.org/10.22610/jeb.v7i4\(j\).592](https://doi.org/10.22610/jeb.v7i4(j).592)
- Ramirez-Peña, M., Mayuet, P. F., Vazquez-Martinez, J. M., & Batista, M. (2020). Sustainability in the Aerospace, Naval, and Automotive Supply Chain 4.0: Descriptive Review. *Materials*, 13(24), 5625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13245625>
- Rasyid, A. (2023). Financial challenge: Are State-Owned banks on the IDX overly dependent on financial ratios? *ATESTASI Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 6(2), 640–649. <https://doi.org/10.57178/atestasi.v6i2.726>
- Roberts, L., Georgiou, N., & Hassan, A. M. (2022). Investigating biodiversity and circular economy disclosure practices: Insights from global firms. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 30(3), 1053–1069. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2402>
- Rosly, A. S., Shafie, R., & Ishak, R. (2024). Corporate Governance Factors and Financial Reporting Timeliness: A Systematic Review and Future research. *PaperAsia*, 40(3b), 121–131. <https://doi.org/10.59953/paperasia.v40i3b.129>
- Shah, D., & Shah, S. (2021). Determinants of manufacturing firms' financial performance in Pakistan. *Journal of Business & Tourism*, 3(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.34260/jbt.v3i2.67>
- Sidhu, A. V., Rastogi, S., Gupte, R., Rawal, A., & Agarwal, B. (2022). Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR) and Bank Performance: A study of the Indian Banks. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(11), 527. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm15110527>
- Sok, P., Snell, L., Lee, W. J., & Sok, K. M. (2017). Linking entrepreneurial orientation and small service firm performance through marketing resources and marketing capability. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*, 27(1), 231–249. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jstp-01-2016-0001>
- Sudrajat, J., & Setiyawati, H. (2021). Role of firm size and profitability on capital structures and its impact over firm value. *Dinasti International Journal of Economics Finance & Accounting*, 2(1), 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.38035/dijefa.v2i1.737>
- Surachman, S. R., & Ningsih, T. (2024). Effect of cash turnover and quick ratio on profitability. *Journal of Economics Management and Entrepreneurship*, 1(2), 94–102. <https://doi.org/10.55208/jeme.v1i2.123>

- Tahmina, T., Garcia, M., Geng, Z., & Bidanda, B. (2022). A survey of smart manufacturing for High-Mix Low-Volume production in defense and aerospace industries. In *Lecture notes in mechanical engineering* (pp. 237–245). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-18326-3_24
- Tekić, D., Mutavdžić, B., Novković, N., Novaković, T., & Vukelić, N. (2020). Analysis of the financial position of mill companies in Vojvodina. *Journal on Processing and Energy in Agriculture*, 24(3–4), 119–122. <https://doi.org/10.5937/jpea24-30296>
- Tiffany, T., & Sufiyati, S. (2023). The analysis of factors affecting profitability. *International Journal of Application on Economics and Business*, 1(1), 603–612. <https://doi.org/10.24912/ijaeb.11.603-612>
- Vuong, N. B., Vu, T. T. Q., & Mitra, P. (2017). Impact of Capital Structure on Firm's Financial Performance: Evidence from United Kingdom. *Journal of Finance & Economic Research*, 2(1), 18–32. <https://doi.org/10.20547/jfer1702102>
- Wang, C., Xie, F., & Xin, X. (2017). CEO inside Debt and Accounting Conservatism. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 35(4), 2131–2159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1911-3846.12372>
- Youness, M. (2023). The impact of political exits on dividend policy. *Proceedings of the . . . International Conference on Business Excellence*, 17(1), 670–680. <https://doi.org/10.2478/picbe-2023-0063>

